

National Identity Clarity or Confusion: English and Urdu Textbooks

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Abstract

The curriculum revision in Pakistan has always been a politically and religiously motivated exercise and this was initiated because of criticism by the religious and political parties. The most recent curriculum revision happened between 2006-2015. The present study looks at the changes made in the textbooks between 2014-2016 and explores the concepts of national identity promoted through the texts. For this study, the textbooks approved by the Punjab Textbook Board and published by different public and private publishers for the academic year 2014-2015 & 2015-2016 were studied. The content of the textbooks was analyzed using the critical discourse analysis approach. The analysis of the textbook content found 'Islam' & 'Muslims' as the common thread amongst all the analyzed textbooks. This thread suggests a single identity, which is synonymous to Islam, 'Pakistanis are Muslims'. This study suggests pluralistic and inclusive content in the textbooks informing students about the TRUE Pakistani society.

1. Introduction

Education in Pakistan is always seen as a key to all its social and economic ills as it is also suggested in the most recent education policy of the government of Pakistan [1]. This policy suggests to all stakeholders to work towards developing learners' critical thinking faculty so that they can contribute in making Pakistan a country safe where all its citizens live together in harmony. The language textbooks are used to inform students about Pakistan's social, political and cultural heritage. The textbook is a very important tool used by the Government of Pakistan to communicate to the learners the image of Pakistan considered important and worthwhile by the state.

The developers and the writers may use the content of the textbooks either upgrade or degrade students' ideas about social issues mentioned above. This study is trying to promote professional critical thinking of those engaged in the process of the textbook, from its conceptualization stage to its printing stage. The content of the textbooks represents a continuous struggle between and amongst different discourses and ideologies each

struggling and competing for dominance. [2]. The content of the textbooks, the stories, poems, bibliography, essays, and dialogues are representative of few groups of Pakistani society and ignores many others groups

2. Research Methodology

2.1. Statement of the Problem

Fairclough [2] suggests that curriculum and textbook writers choose what is included and what is excluded, what is made explicit or left implicit, what is foregrounded and what is backgrounded, what is thematized and what is unthematized, what process types and categories are drawn upon to represent events, and so on. Gee [3] said it in a different way "when we speak or write we always take a particular perspective on what the world is like". The curriculum and textbook writers are both informed and controlled by the language, ideology, social settings and perspective and in turn, they also inform and control others, that is, students, teachers, parents, and families.

The researcher is going to use CDA approach on language textbooks, both English and Urdu, secondary classes, six to ten, which were approved and authorized by the Punjab Textbook Board, Lahore (a body of the Government of the Punjab) and published by different private publishers. This study is aimed at finding at how the other, ethnic and religious groups are presented as Fowler [4] claims, "anything that is said or written about the world is articulated from a particular ideological position".

The content is focused either on confirming the existing social structures and identity or challenge these structures and identities for their failures to construct the perceived national identity of the textbook writers. The analysis of the content will reveal the explicit features and the implicit ideas given through text and images which in effect influence students' understanding of the other, to better understand the ideas put forward and promoted to establish the national identity of students of these textbooks.

2.2. Research question

1. What is the national identity narrative found in English and Urdu textbooks of studied by students of secondary schools?
2. How is the Pakistani nation, its cultural, historical and religious diversity portrayed and represented in the textbooks?

The textbook is one of the tools used all over the world to inform students about a country's social, political, cultural and religious heritage and history. The language textbooks are valued as a very important mouthpiece of a Pakistan state as it portrays and communicates to students what state considers important and worthwhile to be communicated. The stories, dialogues, and images used in language textbooks represent the religious and ethnic minorities, social inequality and cultural and ethnic diversity of a country.

Fairclough's [2] critical discourse analysis approach which in itself is the practical application of the systematic-functional grammar (SFG) developed by Halliday, Matthiessen, and Matthiessen [5] is used to analyze the contents of the textbooks. The SFG discloses the relationship between power and ideology by studying the content, social relations and subject positions in the textbooks. The elements such as ideational, interpersonal and textual functions are considered while examining the contents. Fairclough [2] refers to the content as the writer's personal experiences of the world s/he lives in and people s/he interacts with. Relations show the social relationship established and developed through the text such as family, classmates, colleagues, or friend. The social identity of those who interact in the texts, for example, people belonging to different professions, people living in an area, employee or employer is referred to as subject positions. The dialogue between the reader and the text refers to the content, positions different people assume during this interaction is considered social relations and positions taken during the discourse is called subject positions. Fairclough [2] is aware of the problem with these three elements as he declares that all three (relation, subjects, contents) overlap and co-occur in practice, but it is helpful to be able to distinguish them.

3. Literature Review

3.1. Nationalism and National Identity

Miller [6] has theorized a nation as a political community who control and aspire to control "a chunk of the earth's surface" with the aim of governing themselves, establishing rules and regulation according to the popular political ideology. The scholars have understood nationalism

with primordialist and modernist approaches. The latter group views nation as formed by the history of a nation; the bureaucratic ideas of governance; the rise of industrial economy and capitalism; and spreading of secular norms. The proponents of primordialist approach argue that primordial elements such as historical memories and roots, ethnic origins, symbols and shared myths, language etc. influence the processes of formation of nationalism and national identity. The popular idea of a nation-as-community is accelerated by how people understood time, space and traditions. The invented traditions such as myths about nationalists are sometimes invented but most of the time borrowed and transformed in order to revive them, have also played an important role in forging a nation's understanding of nationhood and national identity.

The proponents of modernist perspective of nationalism and national identity disagree with the ideas that these ideas have any pre-modern origin. For example, Gellner [7] says that 'nationalism is not the awakening of nations to be self-conscious: it invents nations where they do not exist' (p. 169). This perspective is not without its critiques such as Anthony Smith and John Hutchinson who have suggested that nationalism and nation identity is rooted in its primordial elements, especially ethnic origins. Billing's [8] idea of "banal nationalism" found small words rather than grand phrases that generate the unforgettable memories of national identity. The discourse of nationhood is influenced by everything surrounding humans and it is so integrated that we cannot see it with our naked eyes.

Lipowatz & Demertzis [9] argued that nationalism is a political ideology and it can only be created and sustained with three ideological mechanisms which are generalization, naturalization, and identification. Barthes [10] has argued that the interests of an individual are generalized and it appears to be the interests of a group and thus these interests are given priority over other interest. Naturalization is a fundamental function of ideology and "nationalism is the ideology by which the world of nations has come to seem the natural world" and thus what appears natural becomes automatically excused, justified and, in the end, legitimized as suggested. The third element of this process is identification which is a process of unconscious internalization. The process of identification, fully or partially, with a nation's interests and to defend it wherever need and whatever sources required.

Ahmad, Ali, Khan & Khan[11] while analyzing the education policies of Pakistan say that the foremost is the issue of ideology – the role of Islam in curriculum and instruction. They are also aware of the debate going about this issue as they also summarize the views of both the groups. Quaid-e-Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah, the father of the

nation, conceived the education system that develops national character of Pakistani generation. They identified high sense of responsibility, social integrity, selfless service to the nation and morality as the core values that education in Pakistan should strive to develop and promote amongst the Pakistani students.

The education system in Pakistan is focused on developing Islamic identity and this is achieved through education infrastructure, educational material, and educational rules and regulations. This idea of Pakistan by the All India Muslim League was all about Muslims and not about Islam as Noman [12] suggested that the resolution passed in 1940 “can be explained *without reference to Islam* (emphasis original), though not without reference to Muslims”

Raina [13] in his article about religious minorities in Pakistan has identified two major perspectives regarding minorities in Pakistan. The first perspective is that religious minorities are equal citizens of this land and founding fathers of Pakistan never visioned Pakistan as a state where religious minorities would be considered equal to the Muslims, the majority group. This group present as evidence Mr. Jinnah's speech first presidential address to the Pakistan's Constituent Assembly at Karachi on August 11, 1947, before taking over as the first governor-general of Pakistan. Quaid-e-Azam (the great leader) said;

‘religion or caste or creed...has nothing to do with the business of the State’, where ‘no matter what community he belongs, no matter what relations he had with you in the past, no matter what is his colour, caste or creed is first, second and last a citizen of this State with equal rights, privileges and obligation...’, and where ‘we are all citizens and equal citizens of one State’ [14]

The second perspective is that Pakistan movement was all about Islam and Muslims and the purpose was to create a state where Muslims will practice freely the Islamic teachings and all religious minorities will be treated according to the laws Islamic laws prescribed in Koran. Jinnah has used the phrases “true Islamic state”, “Muslim rule”, and his most quoted speech ‘lay the foundation of our democracy on the basis of truly Islamic ideals and principles’ is often quoted to support the second perspective. The religious minorities are subject to a so-called loyalty test to be given a conditional citizenship and not equality.

“[minorities] will be treated as equal citizens with all your rights and obligations so long as you are loyal to Pakistan... Minority communities must not by mere words but by actions show this that they are truly loyal and they must make [the] majority community feel that they are true citizens of Pakistan’ [14].

Jinnah's successor, Liaqat Ali Khan presented and got the so called The Objective Resolution passed through the Constituent Assembly [15]. The Resolution asserts that Allah is sovereign over all “the entire universe” and thus Pakistanis cannot claim to have full authority over their lives and the land but limited and whatever authority they exercise emanates from Koran.

The resolution stated the goal of the state as enabling Muslims to live their lives as per the ‘teachings and requirements of Islam’. The narrative of nationalism and national identity can be summarized as “Pakistan is a Muslim state and its laws will be derived from the teachings of Islam and no law will be made that is contrary to the Islamic teachings. Pakistan will work with all Muslims considered Muslims in the light of the Constitution of the Pakistan and support all Muslims causes and movements. Muslims should be treated fairly and equally in all countries as per the laws of the secular states. Muslim countries should treat religious minorities as per the guidelines given in the Koran.

3.2. Curriculum and Textbook

A study by Durrani & Dunne [16] has researched the “relationship between education and conflict” and found a link between education and its capacity to “exacerbating and ameliorating conflicts”. The curriculum and textbooks in Pakistan have formed the national identity that is rooted in Islam, though it has many opponents of this trend that started in the 1970s. Cohen [17] has argued that Pakistan is seeing the clash between different versions of national identity. The questions such as who is a true Muslim, for whom Pakistan was created, and whose vision should it follow have been discussed vehemently on all platform and it has seeped into the debates around curriculum and textbook too.

Under the 18th Amendment, education is provincial matter but still, Federal Ministry of Education, renamed as Ministry of Federal Education and Professional Training still oversee the formulation of national curriculum though all the four provinces have their own textbook board. The curriculum documents prepared for teachers contain information such as what to teach [content] why to teach [the purpose of teaching a subject], and how to teach [classroom pedagogy and assessment practices]. The textbooks are designed for students and all textbooks are sent to the Curriculum Wing for review and feedback. The textbook boards move to the publishing and distribution of the textbook once Curriculum Wing approves the content of the textbooks. The contents of the textbooks taught all over the country are more or less the same and it represents the state's version of Pakistan, what it should be. The curriculum and textbooks also

represent the thoughts that form the nationalism and the national identity ideas [18].

The content described through different stories and images prescribed in textbook is considered the only source of correct and authentic information for students and thus contribute in constructing the politically legitimate identity constructions. The dominant classroom pedagogy in Pakistani schools is to memorize to recall and students are tested how much they can recall. Kalmus [19] has suggested that in such situations, the hidden messages carried transmitted through textbooks are taken for granted by students as the alternate opinions are non-existent.

The only source of alternate opinion is the teacher who may attempt to transmit the other opinions, missing in the textbook. In such a pedagogical environment textbook yields an enormous institutional authority which shapes the political, social and religious ideologies of students and thus forming their ideas of nationalism and national identity.

Language textbooks as Ndura [20] claims affect students' choice of words and phrases they use, attitudes they display and viewpoints they share in their lives. The various ways texts and images presented in language textbooks have influenced students' communication styles and preferred words and phrases. The contents of language textbooks do not just comprise of words, phrases and sentences to be learned but these texts have power over students as Da Silva [21] suggested in his study. The language curriculum and textbooks very implicitly create, validate, authenticate, authorize and circulate an ideology conceived by the curriculum and textbook writers.

4. Analysis of Findings

4.1. Pakistani identity: Islam and national unity

Religion (Islam) is used by the curriculum and textbook writers to produce and reproduce the notions of what is meant to be by being a Pakistani. The last two national educational policies of Pakistan suggests that Islam is the foundation and Pakistan will only be built on this foundation and without it, Pakistan will lose its distinctions, a country made for the Muslims of South Asia to experience Islamic life [16].

All educational policies have presented Islam as the only framework around which the accepted ideas, values and practices will be encouraged and thus Islam is a significant part of Pakistani identity promoted through textbooks. The policy makers and curriculum developers construct the Pakistani identity around 'oneness', leaving out all the diverse religious, ethnic, linguistic, regional and gender differences. This idea of 'oneness' prevalent in all

education policies till date, curriculum documents and textbooks is "dilution of Pakistani identity" ignoring the multi-ethnic, multi-religious, multicultural dimensions of Pakistan by focusing only on Pakistan as a homogeneous stage and all people are bound together through the Islam.

Table 1. Urdu Textbook

Class 6
Hamd (Poetry) Naat (Poetry) Hajra-e-Aswas ki Kahani (prose) Kidmat-e-khalaq aik abidat (prose) Yum-e-Difa (prose) - slogans of allah awkbar how Islamic state was protected against the non-Muslim aggressor Sehat-o-Safai (prose) - importance of cleanliness in Islam and what prophet said about it Islamic Mumalk ki tanzeem (prose) – alliance against non-muslim countries considered enemies of Muslims
Class 7
Hamd (Poetry) Naat (Poetry) Hajra-e-Aswas ki Kahani (prose) Kidmat-e-khalaq aik abidat (prose) Nazam-o-Zabad (prose) - prophet gave importance to discipline Sab say oncha yeh janda hamara (prose) - the meaning of star, five corners, five pillars of Islam Adab-e-Musharat (prose)- all Muslims are brothers so they should respect each other and forgive mistakes by their brothers
Class 8
Hamd (Poetry) Naat (Poetry) Dara-e-Dil kay wastay paida kia Insan koo, Hazrat Omer bin Abdul Aziz, Iqbal's poem (La illah ill lal lah) Milli Wahdat (prose) - non-Muslim are persecuting Muslims where Muslims are a minority Khawateen ka Makam aur aun kay Hakook (prose) - Islam is the only religion that has given women rights
Class 9 & 10
Hamad (Poetry) Naat (Poetry) Taloah Islam (Poetry) Sadeeq (Poetry) Shan-e-Taqwa (Poetry) Hazrat Omer Farooq (prose) Nazria-e-Pakistan (prose) Safar Kamyabi ki kunji hay (prose) Fatima binat-e-Abdullah (prose)

Table 2 – English Textbook

Class 6
Fair dealing of Hazrat Mohammad (prose)
Class 7
The last sermon of the Rasool Hazrat Muhammad (prose) Eud-ul-Azha (prose)
Class 8
Tolerance of the Holy Prophet (prose) Prayer – (poem) Hazrat Umar (prose)
Class 9 & 10
Kindness of Rasoolullah (prose) Comprehension passages contains stories about early Muslim rulers and prophet Mohammad The translation section contains stories about early Muslim rulers and prophet Mohammad

We are not a country founded on its territorial, linguistic, ethnic, or racial identity. The only justification for our existence is our total commitment to Islam as our sole identity.

The curriculum developers and textbook writers have thought it best to translate these ideas into textbooks by starting each of the book with a Hamd, followed by Naat. The third text is a religious story narrating an event either from Prophet Mohammad's life or from the lives of early Muslim rulers. There is at least 1 narrative text in each book. Each of the analyzed books has indirect references to Islam, Islamic life, Islamic rites and rituals such as Eid Milad-un-Nabi, Eid-ul-Azha.

The stories of various martyrs of 1965 and 1971 wars are also found in these textbooks. These stories have references to Islam and Muslims willing to sacrifice their lives to protect other Muslims and Muslim lands against the non-Muslim aggression. The texts are, in other words, suggesting that all those whose stories are narrated in the textbooks wanted to become martyrs because of their strong Islamic faith and their desire to become a martyr is rooted in Islam, to die while protecting Muslims and an Islamic state.

The Urdu textbooks have about thirty per cent texts (see Table 1) which includes stories about Prophet Mohammad and early Muslim rulers and important people. The stories depicting present day Pakistan and people of Pakistan, its culture also have references to people being Muslims, performing Islamic rites and rituals (prayers, fast and zakat) and celebrating religious festivals (eids). The English textbooks too have many texts (see Table 2), though the percentage of such stories is less than the Urdu textbooks.

5. Discussion

5.1. Pakistani identity and the external other

Edward Said [22] argued that it is essential to establish 'us' and 'others' as the latter is subject to change depending on how the former interpret and reinterpret their differences from the latter. The language textbooks are full of such references where curriculum developers and writers have defined 'us' in very explicit terms and 'others' in implicit ways, that is, what is not 'us' is the 'other'. Kumar [23] called the teaching of official and political history of a country as the process of defining the 'other.' The stories about Syed Ahmad Khan, (Allama) Mohammad Iqbal, (Quaid-e-Azam) Mohammad Ali Jinnah are narrated to emphasize the concept of two-nation theory, highlighting the differences between Muslims and Hindus which became the focal point of Pakistan movement as the texts narrate.

The life stories of army men who were declared martyr by the state are also part of the English and Urdu textbook and all of them are Muslim, which some scholars argued is Pakistan's military's glorification. Hussain [24] says "Pakistan ... needs an antagonist India to define its distinctiveness and maintain internal cohesion". The English and Urdu textbooks are full of religious imagery to enforce and reinforce religious nationalism and defining who is 'us' and the 'other.' This also shows that Islam is the key element that identifies a soldier belonging to Pakistan military and the Indian or a non-Muslim army. These stories also portray Muslims as masculine, determine, strong and heroic and passionate about their country, their Muslim country fellows, and their religion while the 'other' (India or Hindu) are depicted as feminine, defeatist, weak with no desire to protect their country fellows. In the texts, though not explicitly but implicitly the 'other' is defined as non-Muslim,

5.2. National identity and internal 'others'

The textbooks studied in this study shows that Pakistani identity is associated with Islamic identity as there is no reference to other faiths practiced in Pakistan. Miller [6] contends that religious identity and national identity are different as the former does not require physical boundaries while the latter emerges and formed and strengthened in a geographically enclosed place as other national identities also exist in their neighboring countries. There are many religious and political commentators claiming that Pakistan is actually created to make it into a pan-Islamic state which contradicts the founding father's vision of Pakistan who wanted to see it flourish as a multi-culture, multi-faith state. The English and Urdu textbooks depict all Pakistanis as practicing Muslims, women cover their heads

whether they are in their houses or out, doing different chores. The Curriculum objectives of the religious texts either prose or poetry focus on making the readers good Muslims who are aware of how to live their lives according to the Islamic teachings by following the life stories of Prophet Mohammad and the early Muslim rulers and people close to Prophet Mohammad. For example, the Kalash tribe found in the Northern areas of Pakistan, which is now part of the newly created province called Gilgit-Baltistan. This area is also home to many Buddhist era ruins. The English and Urdu textbooks do not have a single word about this group, thus making them as the other. There is a small religious group named Zoroastrian that has been living in areas that became Pakistan at the time of partition of the Indian subcontinent. The students remain unaware of the existence of these two ethnic and religious groups as the textbooks are not considered an appropriate tool to make students aware of all faiths and ethnic groups practiced in Pakistan. This trend shows that only those groups are included in the texts which fall under the category of national identity which is synonymous to Muslim identity, thus excluding many millions of people living in Pakistan. Durrani & Dunne [16] puts it this way "...while unifying Pakistani Muslims, it alienates non-Muslim Pakistanis" in their study while analyzing how curriculum of Social Studies taught in Pakistan shaping students views about non-Muslims. The textbooks analyzed in this study contains not a single story about non-Muslim Pakistani and no mention is made of non-Muslims living in Pakistan, how they are, their religion, religious festivals etc. The only heroes who can be given space in the textbooks are Muslims as all non-Muslims are considered enemies of Islamic Pakistan.

6. References

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